

Original Article

Influence of Virtual Reality on Self-efficacy of Stroke Survivors: A Scoping Review of Literature.

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ABSTRACT

Background

Recent trends point to virtual reality as a useful intervention strategy facilitating post-stroke recovery. Several studies have been reported to address different forms of self-efficacy that significantly influence rehabilitation outcomes post-stroke. Since virtual reality intervention can be devised based on the four principles of Bandura's self-efficacy theory, it can enhance self-efficacy in stroke survivors. This review examines whether the extant literature finds virtual reality (VR) interventions beneficial in improving self-efficacy in stroke survivor.

Materials and Methods: A search of databases like PubMed using search terms related to “virtual reality”, “self-efficacy” and “stroke” was performed. Peer-reviewed articles in English that met the inclusion criteria were selected. Gray literature and those without self-efficacy as the primary outcome were excluded. Data extraction was done from the selected articles and narrative synthesis was done. The guidelines led by Arksey and O’Malley and PRISMA Scr for scoping reviews were used to report findings.

Results: After screening 65 articles related to the topic retrieved from databases like PubMed, Web of Science, and Cochrane, only 9 were found suitable for synthesis after excluding irrelevant articles. The key findings from the selected studies reflected that virtual reality used standalone or along with other interventions improved self-efficacy, whether domain-specific or generalized self-efficacy.

Conclusion:

Virtual reality seems more promising than standard rehabilitation interventions in improving self-efficacy. Further studies are required to establish its benefit with confidence.

Keywords: self-efficacy, stroke, virtual reality, scoping review.

Introduction:

The majority of the individuals who have suffered a stroke have significant motor and non-motor deficits. But, what makes it more challenging is the long duration of recovery. Globally, there are about 12.2 million new cases of stroke every year of which a significant number of stroke patients suffer from moderate to severe disability and require assistance from others in daily activities [^{1,2}].

The complex needs arising require concerted rehabilitation strategies, a person's motivation, and efforts to overcome barriers. Studies have shown successful rehabilitation is influenced by the self-efficacy of the individual. It is defined by Bandura as the belief in one's ability to meet challenges and achieve goals [3]. Hence, the ability to persevere, strategize, and take responsibility for one's health is influenced by one's perception of self-efficacy which plays a significant role in optimal rehabilitation, particularly in chronic illnesses like stroke.

Traditionally stroke rehabilitation focuses more on motor recovery with disregard for cognitive or psychological issues. Research has also identified issues involving stroke survivors' low level of interest in adhering to rehabilitative interventions and the effects of low adherence [4,5]. Emerging interventions in neuro-rehabilitation like virtual reality offer avenues to augment and provide holistic therapy including psychological benefits and physical movements.

Virtual reality (VR) is characterized by computer-based simulation of real-world events or objects [6]. In comparison to conventional therapies, therapeutic VR demonstrates several advantages viz. immediate feedback, optimal motor learning due to multiple repetitions, enhanced motivation, and participation [7]. Despite a few barriers like the learning curve, accessibility, and comfort level which impact its clinical application; many recent studies have utilized virtual reality programs in stroke rehabilitation. By increasing subjects' interest and rate of participation, virtual reality training programs increase functional activity and influence brain reorganization by increasing neural plasticity in stroke patients [7]. An integrative review of 13 RCTs and quasi-experimental controlled trials elucidated significant improvements in balance, upper limb motor function, and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) following the use of VR-based commercial video games [8]. Similarly, Another systematic review [8] highlighted the benefits of VR in improving cognitive

functions, motor skills, and health-related quality of life among stroke survivors. However, its specific effect on self-efficacy remains largely unexplored [8].

In the context of Bandura's social cognition theory, VR can provide task-oriented, imitative, and repetitive activities resulting in a positive transfer of learning from the virtual environment to real-world activity [9] and also has the advantage of integrating the self-efficacy-related four principles. The four principles are (1) mastery experience or successful performance of the activity of interest through repetition (2) verbal persuasion, or feedback or encouragement, given by a trusted source that the individual is capable of performing the activity of interest; (3) modeling or vicarious experience or seeing other individuals perform the same activity of interest in a similar situation and (4) physiological and affective states such as mood, anxiety, pain, fatigue, hunger, or dizziness associated with a given activity [3]. The immersive and interactive nature allows VR to provide active participation, immediate feedback, and task customization opportunities. Participants could gain mastery through repetitive activities. Indirect experiences of the activity can be gained through the model represented on the screen, while, therapists and families can provide appropriate feedback during the training. The stronger an individual's self-efficacy and outcome expectations are, the more likely it is that the individual will put in more effort with a given activity. Thus, VR offers both motor and psychological interventions by improving mood, motivation, and acceptance of illness which in turn boosts self-efficacy [10]. This research endeavors to gain valuable insights into VR interventions' value to empower stroke survivors to navigate challenges with confidence and resilience.

Aims and objectives: This study explores the influence of virtual reality intervention on self-efficacy post-stroke.

Research question: whether virtual reality intervention can increase the self-efficacy of stroke survivors?

Methods:

The impact of virtual reality on self-efficacy in stroke survivors has not been comprehensively reviewed previously, hence a scoping review seemed to be an appropriate methodology. The current scoping review follows the methodological framework of Arksey and O'Malley [11]. It consists of the following steps: (1) identifying the research questions, (2) identifying relevant studies, (3) study selection, (4) data extraction and synthesis (5) collating, summarizing, and reporting the results adhering to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) [12] and consultation with stakeholders (optional). The scoping review was registered retrospectively in Open science framework (osf.io/fg5ca).

Search strategy

Systematic Screening of databases “PubMed”, “Web of Science” and “Cochrane” was done based on search strategy related to the terms “ virtual reality”, “ self- efficacy” and “stroke” using boolean operators “and”, “or”. Appendix 1 represents the search strategy.

Appendix 1

S. No.	Primary search terms	Related search strings
1.	Virtual reality (VR)	VR, Virtual technology, Virtual Environment (VE), Immersive Virtual Reality
2.	Self-efficacy	Self- Efficacy, Self Esteem, Self-Concept, Self Confidence
3.	Stroke	Post- Stroke, Stroke Survivors, Stroke Rehabilitation, Stroke patients, CVA

Inclusion Criteria:

Study Design: Randomized controlled trials (RCTs), Case studies, Observational, Experimental, and Quasi-experimental studies

Population: Adults diagnosed with stroke of any type or severity.

Intervention: Virtual reality-based interventions targeting self-efficacy in stroke rehabilitation.

Comparison: Studies with a control group receiving conventional care or alternative interventions.

Outcome Measures: Studies reporting quantitative measures of self-efficacy using standardized tools.

Language: English-language studies.

Publication Date: Studies published within the last 20 years (from year January 2004- December 2024).

Exclusion criteria:

Studies on neurological conditions other than stroke, augmented reality alone or mixed reality and not measuring self-efficacy as an outcome were excluded.

Selection of articles.

All articles in the English language published in peer-reviewed journals were included. Grey literature, book chapters, and abstracts only were excluded. Initial screening was done for title and abstract based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria followed by a full-text screening to select relevant studies. References of those studies were screened manually for any other eligible study. The final selection was based on the consensus of both the authors and the result was presented using PRISMA Scr flowchart.

Data extraction and synthesis

The data extraction was done in a pre-determined format in Microsoft Excel based on its relevance to the research question. Synthesis was done based on common findings.

Results and Discussion:

The search of databases returned 172 articles with the retrieval of 65 articles after applying filters and removing duplicates. Furthermore, by removing study protocols, and preprints, and selecting those that met the inclusion criteria, 9 articles were found and selected for final synthesis (Fig 1).

Fig 1. Flowchart of the process of selection of articles (based on Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines).

The Study characteristics are summarized in Table 1 and the quality rating of the selected articles are displayed in Table 2 :

There were 9 studies [13-21] with N=400 subjects selected from clinical settings/hospital/rehabilitation centers from Korea (3), China (2), Canada (1), Spain (1), Taiwan (1) and Poland (1). All of the studies were RCTs with only one single subject proof of principle (feasibility) study [18] and one case series with 3 subjects [17]. Two of them explicitly had VR interventions based on the 4 principles of Bandura's self-efficacy theory. Two studies used SSEQ and one used GSES as outcome measures based on holistic self-efficacy [14-16] while three others measured Balance self-efficacy through the ABC scale and one of the studies used the MTR self-efficacy scale as the outcome measure based on domain-specific self-efficacy [18-21].

Finally, 9 studies were selected for narrative synthesis. Out of which two studies exclusively focused on virtual reality alone [18,20]. Seven studies examined virtual reality along with other interventions [13-16,19-21], while four studies compared VR to other interventions on self-efficacy [13,17,18,20]. Additionally, two studies reported outcomes of VR on domain-specific self-efficacy [18,21]; another three studies reported outcomes of VR on holistic self-efficacy [16,14,15]. It is noteworthy that these studies overlapped across the categories. The included studies used a range of VR types, from non-immersive (such as screen-based systems) [13,16,21] to semi-immersive (such as virtual environments without head-mounted display) [18,20] and fully immersive (such as those using head-mounted displays) [14,15,17,19] demonstrating the diverse approaches being used in stroke.

The summary of the selected studies is as below: (Table 1)

Table 1: Summarises the selected studies

S. No.	Author & Year	Country	Study Type	Subject	Intervention & Dosage	Type of VR	Outcome Measure (self-efficacy)	Findings
1.	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023) [13]	South Korea	RCT	N=43	VR+KT Vs VR Dosage: 35 mins/session, 5x/week, 6 weeks (30 sessions in total)	Non-Immersive VR	Self-Efficacy Scale (SEF)	Both VR training groups improved hand function and self-efficacy, but the combined VR and KT groups showed greater improvement.
2.	Park and Ha. (2023) [14]	South Korea	RCT	N=60	VR+CT Vs CCT Vs CT Dosage: 30 mins/session, 5x/week, 8 weeks (40 sessions in total)	Immersive VR	SSEQ	The VR group showed significant improvements in cognitive function, self-efficacy, attention, and memory compared to the control groups.
3.	Kiper <i>et al.</i> (2022) [15]	Poland	randomized controlled trial with a blinded outcome assessor	N=60	VR+CT Vs CT Dosage: 30 mins/session, 5x/week, 3 weeks (15 sessions in total)	Immersive VR	Generalised Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES)	The applied VR therapy significantly increased the sense of self-efficacy and the level of acceptance of the illness; however, this effect was similar to that obtained with the standard intervention.

4.	Long <i>et al.</i> (2020) [16]	China	RCT Assessor blind Random allocation	N= 60	VR+CT Vs CT Dosage: 45 mins/session, 5x times/week, 3 weeks (15 sessions in total)	Non-Immersive VR	SSEQ	VR training could be used as an effective tool to enhance self-efficacy and improve ADL of patients with stroke in acute hospitals. Limitations _ small sample size. VR activities are not always a real-life simulation Recommendations- more studies needed
5.	Cortés-Pérez <i>et al.</i> (2020) [17]	Spain	Case series	N=3	VR+CT Vs VR Vs CT Dosage: 45 mins/session, 3x/week, 8 weeks (24 sessions in total)	Immersive VR	ABC & Falls self-efficacy	Immersive VR improves balance and reduces the risk of falls,
6.	Richards <i>et al.</i> (2018) [18]	Canada	A proof of principle study (Feasibility study)	N=1	VR Vs CT Dosage: 30 mins/session, 3x /week , 6 weeks (18 sessions in total)	Semi-immersive VR	Activities specific Balance Confidence scale	The VR training led to an additional increase in speed as measured by walking 5 meters as fast as possible and distance walking in 6 minutes, as well as improved balance self-efficacy and anticipatory locomotor adjustments.

7.	Jung <i>et al.</i> (2012) [19]	South Korea	randomized, pretest-posttest control group design.	N=21	VR+TD Vs TD (CG) Dosage: 30 mins/session, 3x /week , 6 weeks (18 sessions in total)	Immersive VR	The Activities Specific Balance Confidence (ABC)	VR + treadmill group showed significant improvement in both balance and balance self-efficacy compared to the control group (only treadmill)
8.	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2008) [20]	Taiwan (Republic of)	RCT	N=24	VR Vs CT Dosage: 60 mins/session, 5x/week, 4 weeks (12 sessions in total)	Semi-immersive VR	ABC	VR improves balance self-efficacy.
9.	Lam <i>et al.</i> (2006) [21]	China (Hong Kong)	RCT	N= 58	2DVR+ Psychoeducation Vs CT Dosage: 60 mins/session, 3x/week, 4 weeks (12 sessions in total)	Non-immersive VR	MTR self-efficacy	The subjects of both training groups (2DVR and video psychoeducation group) showed a significant improvement in their knowledge, skills, and self-efficacy in using the MTR ($p < 0.01$), whereas, the MTR skills and self-efficacy of the control group remained stable over a four-week interval

- Where VR-virtual reality, KT-Kinesiotaping, CT-conventional training, TD-tread mill, CG-control group, CCT-computer assisted cognitive training, 2DVR- 2-D virtual reality.

Further, the JADAD scale or Oxford quality rating system was used to rate the quality of the included studies. (Table 2) The scale comprises a total score of five (two for randomization, two for blinding, and one for dropout rate). Items in each of the three dimensions needed to be mentioned in the text to receive a score of 1 for each item. Inappropriate or general mention was not scored. A total score of 3 or more is considered high quality whereas 2 or less meant low quality RCT [22].

Table 2: JADAD Score /Oxford Quality rating

Studies	Randomisation: Was the study described as randomized (this includes the use of words such as randomly, random, and randomization)?		Blinding: Was the study described as double blind?		Drop outs: Was there a description of withdrawals and dropouts?	Total score
	Criteria 1	Criteria 2	Criteria 3	Criteria 4	Criteria 5	
Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023) [13]	1	1	0	0	1	3/5
Park and Ha.(2023) [14]	1	1	0	1	1	4/5
Kiper <i>et al.</i> (2022) [15]	1	1	1	0	1	4/5
Cortés-Pérez <i>et al.</i> (2020) [16]	na	na	na	na	na	na
Long <i>et al.</i> (2020) [17]	1	1	1	1	1	5/5
Richards <i>et al.</i> (2018) [18]	na	na	na	na	na	na
Jung <i>et al.</i> (2012) [19]	1	1	1	0	1	4/5
Yang <i>et al.</i> (2008) [20]	1	1	0	1	1	4/5
Lam <i>et al.</i> (2006) [21]	1	0	1	0	0	2/5

- Criteria 1 and 2- randomization; score 1 point each if randomization and the method to generate sequence is mentioned appropriately; deduct one if the method of sequence generation is inappropriate
- Criteria 3 and 4 – blinding; score 1 point each for double-blind and the method of blinding is appropriate; deduct 1 if the method is inappropriate.
- Criteria 5-drop outs; a score of 1 point is given for describing dropouts.

This scoping review reports the effect of virtual reality on self-efficacy in persons with stroke. Though the selected studies originated from different countries, the majority were from South Korea and China, pointing towards regional advancement in the use of VR in stroke rehabilitation, while limiting generalisability. The key findings that emerged aligned with the research question and objectives of this review:

1) Effectiveness of the VR interventions at improving self-efficacy in stroke

In our review most of the studies found out that VR irrespective of the types viz immersive, non-immersive and semi-immersive were generally effective to increase self-efficacy post stroke. Similar findings by Maiers *et al.*[²³] reported that specific VR-based stroke rehabilitation showed better results than non-specific recreational-based VR stroke rehabilitation.

1.1) Effect of Standalone Virtual Reality Intervention and as an Adjunct, or in comparison to Other Interventions

Several authors [^{13,18}] reported that VR alone increases self-efficacy in community ambulation, while another group [²⁴] found weak evidence using standalone VR therapy. It can be inferred that there is no clear-cut evidence of the impact of virtual reality alone on boosting self-efficacy due to the inadequate number of studies. Similarly, some studies suggested that a combined approach may yield greater improvements in certain outcomes, such as hand function, cognitive aspects, and self-efficacy[^{13,15}] compared to VR alone or conventional therapy. Jung *et al.*[²⁰] concluded that an additional 3 weeks of virtual reality treadmill training was more effective than treadmill training alone in improving balance

control and self-efficacy^[20]. These findings underscore the need for further research to understand the comparative effectiveness of different treatment approaches.

1.2 Effect of Virtual Reality on Domain specific and Holistic Self-efficacy

Numerous systematic reviews have examined VR in different functional contexts, but none specifically in the context of self-efficacy in stroke. Our review identified a few studies focused on specific domains, such as balance self-efficacy, while others examined self-efficacy more broadly^[14-16,18-21]. It has been observed that a certain amount of self-efficacy is required to participate in VR-related intervention, which further increases self-efficacy, whether holistic or domain-specific.

2) How does VR improve self-efficacy? (mechanism of action, potential, and challenges)

It's evident from this review that VR therapy holds promise in improving self-efficacy among stroke survivors beyond motor rehabilitation. With opportunities for repetitive and controlled actions facilitating mastery experiences (such as successfully finishing tasks like popping colored fish), VR supports gradual skill acquisition and consistent success. It also offers vicarious experiences through virtual scenarios, incorporates verbal encouragement via guided therapeutic interactions, and lowers physiological barriers by creating a controlled, stress-free environment, resonating with Bandura's self-efficacy principles. Our findings are consistent with those reported by Barclay *et al.* ^[24] and Shausssney *et al.* ^[25]. The engaging nature of VR interventions serves as a positive distraction for the patients, leading to better adherence to treatment and decreased drop-outs from therapy.

However, there are several limitations to the clinical applications of VR interventions due to the inability to fully simulate real-life activities [6], high cost, and lack of accessibility in underserved regions. Also, technological adoption for older adults or those with limited digital literacy may be difficult due to the learning curve. Immersive VR can be uncomfortable for those with sensory overload issues. Solutions include low-cost mobile technology, cost-sharing models during procurement of VR, using telehealth in underserved areas, simplified & user-friendly interfaces, and tailored training. Gradual desensitization or semi-immersive/ non-immersive VR can be offered as an alternative for those experiencing discomfort.

3) Methodological considerations

3.1) Heterogeneity of studies

In this review, the types of virtual reality and the number of intervention components differed. Our findings support the literature, which shows that Immersive virtual reality training increased motivation and engagement in stroke patients, while non-immersive VR improved fine motor skills and coordination, catering to specific rehabilitation outcomes [26].

Additionally, heterogeneity was observed, as the studies used various outcome measures for holistic self-efficacy and domain-specific self-efficacy, as well as different dosages. The dosage (intensity, frequency, and duration) varied across the studies, ranging from 30- 60 mins, 3x-5x/week for around 3-8 weeks of interventions. Moreover, variations were noted in the outcome based on the types of VR interventions. This limited the comparability and generalizability of the included studies significantly. Hence, standard validated measures

with adequate psychometrics and optimal dosage protocols must be developed and used in future research.

3.2) Quality of Studies

The quality rating of the 7 RCTs among the included studies showed that all the RCTs had adequate or good quality (score $>3/5$), except for one study by Lam *et al.* [21], which scored a 2/5, indicating poor quality. Since the study was conducted in 2006, it may have used a dated methodology. Being a scoping review, it was decided to retain it to ensure comprehensiveness.

Suggestions for optimal outcome:

Based on the analysis of the selected studies, for optimal outcome in clinical application a dosage, ranging from 3 weeks to 8 weeks (VR standalone) or 3 weeks of VR in addition to standard care, is recommended. Most of the studies have used immersive VR to achieve a greater psychological effect of VR. Hence, an Immersive virtual environment is deemed necessary. Focused interventions like Erickson's psychotherapy can also be incorporated for added benefit in VR therapy to improve self-efficacy.

Limitations:

There might be inherent biases due to the methodology of the scoping review. The generalizability of the findings of the selected studies is limited by the methodological limitations, like a lack of a control group and a small sample size.

Future recommendations:

In future longitudinal studies, may be undertaken to see the stability of improvement in self-efficacy following VR intervention. There is a need for rigorous study protocols for undertaking high quality RCTS with sufficient sample sizes, standardized tools and long-term follow-ups to ensure reliability and applicability of results.

Further mapping of studies from other databases and including studies in languages other than English can be used to develop a comprehensive review. RCT can be used to compare VR directly with conventional treatment for its relative impact on self-efficacy. It would be imperative to compare the different types of VR (immersive, non-immersive, and semi-immersive; specific and non-specific) interventions on self-efficacy.

Clinical implications:

Since the focus at present is on the real-world translation of gains through any intervention, virtual reality seems to capture the essence as a powerful medium to simulate activities in real life. Hence, it provides insight into the nature of performance, including challenges and barriers. The affordability and accessibility of VR currently affect its use beyond research tools into day-to-day clinical practice.

Conclusion

Even though virtual reality has the potential to improve self-efficacy post-stroke when used singularly or in conjunction with other interventions, more studies are needed to build up a guideline for its clinical use.

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